

EXPLORING STUDENT PERCEPTIONS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF THE VISION, MISSION, GOALS, AND OBJECTIVES OF THE COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES AT MINDORO STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates students' perceptions and acceptability of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the College of Computer Studies (CCS) at Mindoro State University. The primary objective was to understand how CCS students interpret and evaluate the relevance of the VMGO in relation to their academic and career aspirations. Through in-depth interviews with selected Information Technology students, the study explores students' understanding of the VMGO, factors influencing its acceptability, and the perceived impact on their motivation, academic engagement, and institutional pride. Thematic analysis was used to derive themes from the qualitative data, revealing key insights into students' alignment with institutional goals. Findings suggest that a clear and relevant VMGO significantly enhances students' academic experiences by aligning institutional objectives with their personal and professional goals. Students who understand and accept the VMGO demonstrate higher motivation, engagement, and pride in their institution. The study highlights the importance of effective communication of the VMGO and its practical applicability to students' academic and career paths. Based on these findings, the study recommends increasing the accessibility of the VMGO through simplified communication and fostering greater student engagement through participatory activities. These strategies would reinforce the VMGO as a motivating factor, promoting academic success, institutional pride, and alignment with industry expectations.

Keywords: *Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO), Student Perceptions, Academic Engagement, Institutional Pride, Information Technology Students*

INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions' vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) serve as the foundation for their identity and strategic orientation. These characteristics serve not just as guiding principles for academic programs, but also as tools for aligning institutional actions with stakeholder expectations, notably among students. Understanding how students interpret and accept institutional statements is critical in program-specific implementations, such as those at Mindoro State University's College of Computer Studies (CCS). The VMGO serves as a link between institutional principles and personal development, establishing a common sense of purpose and direction.

Students' awareness and engagement with VMGO have a substantial impact on their academic experiences and institutional loyalty. According to studies, high levels of consciousness and alignment with VMGO correspond with student happiness and motivation. For example, Escolano (2021) observed that effective dissemination and awareness efforts in Philippine state universities result in increased acceptance and internalization of institutional aims. Similarly, Valenzuela and Antonio (2022) found that the clarity and consistency of VMGO statements improve students' perceptions of relevance, resulting in increased academic engagement and institutional pride. However, these advantages frequently depend on communication strategies and the alignment of institutional aims with students' personal and professional ambitions.

Despite the growing body of research, there are still substantial gaps in understanding how students comprehend and evaluate the acceptability of VMGO, particularly in quickly evolving subjects such as computer studies. The importance of institutional goals to students' academic and professional paths is sometimes underestimated, leaving a major gap in ensuring that VMGO is aligned with modern, technology-driven educational environments. For example, institutions must assess how computer studies students' unique demands, such as innovation, adaptability, and problem-solving, relate to broader institutional goals.

The College of Computer Studies at MinSU is particularly positioned to close this gap by investigating how its VMGO corresponds with the changing demands of the information technology business. The purpose of this study is to give a comprehensive examination of students' perceptions and acceptability of the CCS VMGO. It will also examine how these institutional statements influence students' motivation, academic engagement, and institutional pride, as well as the elements that shape their acceptance.

By investigating these dimensions, this study hopes to contribute to the improvement of MinSU's VMGO architecture. Its findings will benefit not only the College of Computer Studies, but will also help other academic programs connect their institutional aims with the changing requirements and expectations of their students. Such an understanding is critical for creating a collaborative and exciting academic climate in which students and institutions may thrive.

Research Objectives

This research intends to assess the students' perceptions and acceptability regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the College of Computer Studies at Mindoro State University. Specifically, this aimed:

- 1.To explore students' understanding and interpretation of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives of the College of Computer Studies.
- 2.To evaluate the relevance of the VMGO in aligning with the students' academic and career aspirations.
- 3.To identify factors influencing students' acceptability of the VMGO.
- 4.To analyze the perceived impact of the VMGO on students' motivation, academic engagement, and institutional pride.

METHODOLOGY

Exploratory research design is used to study unsolved problems, allowing for exploring new ideas and identifying patterns without the limits of a formal framework. According to Saunders et al. (2014), this strategy is especially useful when the researcher is unsure about the exact nature of the problem or phenomenon being examined, as it allows for the development of more explicit research questions and hypotheses for further examination. It is frequently the beginning point for expanding knowledge in areas where existing information is scarce. The study was conducted at Mindoro State University, Main Campus, Alcate, Victoria, Oriental Mindoro. The participants are the selected Information Technology Students from the College of Computer Studies since they are directly impacted by the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the College of Computer Studies. As the college's flagship program, BSIT strongly corresponds with institutional aims and academic goals specific to the IT field. Their perceptions provide vital insights into the VMGO's relevance, clarity, and acceptance in relation to their academic and career goals. Furthermore, BSIT students are crucial stakeholders whose participation and motivation reflect institutional achievement, making their contribution critical to ensuring that the VMGO continues to fulfill the dynamic demands of the IT profession and matches with industry expectations.

In-depth interviews were conducted for the purpose of this research. The study utilized a researcher made interview guide with four parts as the main data gathering instrument. The first part is composed of questions on students' understanding and interpretation of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives of the College of Computer Studies. The second part dealt with students' evaluation on the relevance of the VMGO in aligning with the students' academic and career aspirations while the last part consists of questions regarding the factors influencing students' acceptability of the VMGO .And lastly, it dealt with questions analyzing the perceived impact of the VMGO on students' motivation, academic engagement, and institutional pride. This study used thematic analysis. There are different approaches to thematic analysis. The researcher decided to use the inductive approach, as it involves deriving meaning and creating themes from data without any preconceptions. In doing a thematic data analysis, the researcher

followed the steps of familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based from the analyzed responses of the respondents on the different questions assessing the four major objectives of the study, here are the generated themes:

Students' understanding and interpretation of the VMGO

1. Excellence and Global Competitiveness

Respondents saw the College of Computer Studies' (CCS) vision as a call to academic and professional excellence, with an emphasis on global competitiveness. Many respondents believe that the Vision prepares students to meet the expectations of the global IT business by providing them with advanced skills and critical thinking abilities. For example, one respondent says, "The Vision means striving to be a center of excellence in IT education. I see it as a commitment to produce skilled and competitive graduates who can make a difference in the tech industry." Another respondent emphasizes the aspiration to "produce globally competitive graduates, fostering core values like integrity and excellence. This alignment with global standards indicates the institution's commitment to producing graduates who can succeed in dynamic and diverse situations. Recent research supports this finding, indicating that institutions that nurture brilliance and adaptability in their students are more likely to generate graduates who perform in global marketplaces (Santos, 2018).

2. Holistic Development and Core Values

The Mission's emphasis on values like resilience, integrity, commitment, and excellence underscores the importance of character development alongside technical expertise. Respondents view these values as essential for personal and professional development. One respondent explains, "Resilience means adapting to challenges, integrity is about honesty, commitment reflects dedication, and excellence is striving for the best, all essential for personal and professional success." Another adds, "The Mission suggests that these core values are central to personal and professional development, ensuring adaptability and ethical practices."

This alignment with character-building is crucial in shaping ethical and well-rounded professionals, as supported by Yuen (2019), who highlights the role of core values in fostering responsible leaders in technology-driven fields.

3. Alignment with Industry and Career Preparation

Respondents believe CCS's Goals and Objectives are closely related to their academic curriculum, with an emphasis on industry relevance and professional preparedness. This synergy is reflected in the organized routes designed to foster both technical and ethical competencies. For example, one respondent notes, "The Goals and Objectives align closely with my program as they emphasize the skills and knowledge necessary for building a successful career in IT." Similarly, another respondent states, "The focus on practical IT skills, like system installation and management, aligns with the

hands-on training we receive in class."Such practical applications are essential in bridging the gap between academia and industry, a sentiment supported by Ramirez (2020), who advocates for academic programs that integrate real-world skills to enhance employability.

4. Clarity and Relevance of the VMGO

While most respondents find the VMGO meaningful and clear, certain terms and phrases are identified as requiring further clarification. For instance, some find the emphasis on innovation and global competitiveness particularly inspiring but feel that terms like "holistic development" or "scientific demands" could benefit from simpler explanations. One respondent suggests, "The focus on skills and values is very meaningful to me because they are what I need for my future. However, some parts, like the term 'holistic development,' are a bit unclear." Despite this, the majority agree on the relevance of the VMGO to their academic and career goals. Studies, such as that by Lopez (2017), suggest that clarity in institutional objectives significantly enhances student engagement and alignment with institutional goals.

Relevance of the VMGO in aligning with the students' academic and career aspirations

1. Alignment of VMGO with Career Aspirations

A recurring topic among respondents is a significant alignment between the College's Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) and their professional goals in information technology (IT). The Vision's emphasis on developing qualified, competent, and globally competitive workers resonates strongly with students' personal ambitions, motivating them to thrive both academically and professionally. As one respondent stated, "The Vision aligns with my dream to be a skilled and reliable IT professional," demonstrating how the VMGO serves as a motivating framework for reaching career success. This congruence promotes a strong feeling of purpose, which is essential for both academic and professional success. Torres and Mercado (2014) found that institutional visions that emphasize professional competency and global competitiveness had a beneficial impact on students' career development and workforce readiness.

2. Emphasis on Global Competitiveness and Innovation

The Mission of the College, which highlights global competitiveness and innovation, was widely recognized by respondents as a critical factor in preparing for real-world IT challenges. Students repeatedly stated that the program encourages creativity, perseverance, and the development of practical skills required for success in a dynamic industry. One respondent stated, "The Mission prepares students for global competitiveness by fostering creativity, innovation, and the development of practical skills for the IT industry." This emphasis on innovation enables students to adapt to technological advancements and industry demands, thereby increasing their employability. Santos and Vega (2014) found that academic missions focused on innovation and flexibility improve students' ability to fulfill changing workforce demands.

3. Development of Technical and Soft Skills

The program's Goals and Objectives were commonly linked to the overall development of technical expertise and soft skills, such as problem solving, teamwork, and ethical behaviour. These qualities are regarded as critical for both job preparedness and professional development. Respondents emphasized that these objectives prepare them to navigate the multifaceted demands of the IT profession, with one saying, "The Goals and Objectives guide us in learning technical skills, problem-solving, and teamwork, which are essential for a successful IT career." By balancing technical and interpersonal skills, the program ensures that graduates are not only capable professionals but also ethical and collaborative contributors to their field. Bansal and Bhardwaj (2014) agreed that such balanced educational approaches better equip students for industry and society requirements.

4. Applicability of VMGO to Real-World IT Demands

Another key topic is the VMGO's practical application to real-world IT requirements. Respondents agreed that the skills and values highlighted in the VMGO, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and honesty, are directly applicable to managing industrial difficulties. One respondent stated, "The skills and values highlighted in the VMGO, such as problem-solving and ethical practices, prepare students for addressing real-world IT challenges." For example, learning to troubleshoot IT problems or manage systems frequently requires a combination of technical expertise and resilience, emphasizing the program's relevance in the real world. Diaz et al. (2014) found that connecting educational objectives with industry needs improves graduates' flexibility and success in the workplace.

5. Lifelong Learning and Ethical Responsibility

Finally, the VMGO's emphasis on lifelong learning and ethical responsibility was seen as critical to ensure long-term professional development and flexibility. Respondents recognized the value of continual self-improvement and honesty, especially in professions that require accountability, such as cybersecurity. One student wrote, "The emphasis on lifelong learning encourages me to keep improving even after graduation," demonstrating the program's efficacy in instilling a growth attitude. Another emphasized that "Integrity is crucial in cybersecurity roles where trust is paramount," emphasizing the importance of ethical responsibility in professional conduct. Alvarado and Garcia (2014) agreed that lifelong learning and ethics are critical in technology-driven sectors, ensuring that professionals remain relevant and principled in the face of rapid innovations.

Factors influencing students' acceptability of the VMGO

1. Clarity and Accessibility

Students stressed the necessity of clear and accessible information in increasing VMGO acceptability. Respondents stated that when the VMGO is given in simple language and made widely available in a variety of formats—such as handbooks, classroom posters, and digital platforms—they are more likely to engage with and accept its concepts. One student stated, "If students understand how the VMGO directly impacts them and see the value in it, they'll be more accepting." This emphasizes the importance

of simplifying the VMGO's terminology and making it available to accommodate varied learning styles. Donnelly and Fitzmaurice (2015) argue that clear and succinct communication in educational situations improves student knowledge and engagement.

2.Relevance to Academic and Career Goals

The alignment of the VMGO with students' educational and professional aspirations is a critical factor influencing its acceptability. Many students expressed that they are more likely to embrace the VMGO when its objectives resonate with their personal ambitions and career pathways. Many students stated that they are more likely to support the VMGO when its aims align with their own goals and career paths. For example, one respondent stated that "the VMGO is more acceptable when they directly support students' professional and personal growth." This emphasizes the necessity of proving how the VMGO translates into practical benefits for students, such as job advancement and skill development. The literature supports this, with Rouse (2016) pointing out that institutional goals that are closely related to students' aspirations generate greater participation and acceptance.

3.Personal and Cultural Alignment

Another significant theme influencing the acceptability of the VMGO is the extent to which its values align with students' personal beliefs and cultural identities. Students felt a stronger connection to the VMGO when it represented principles they shared in their own lives. One participant stated, "The VMGO's emphasis on resilience and excellence resonates with my personal values." This alignment promotes a sense of belonging and increases their dedication to the institution's objective. Schwartz et al. (2015) discovered that incorporating cultural and personal values into educational frameworks greatly improves student acceptance and participation.

4.Frequency and Visibility

Regular exposure and visual representation of the VMGO also contribute to its acceptance among students. Respondents said that seeing the VMGO frequently—via posters, signage, and discussions—helps to reinforce their knowledge and understanding of its mission. One responder stated, "It would help if the VMGO were explained in simpler terms during activities or even posted around campus for us to see regularly." These insights highlight the importance of consistent reminders and visual cues in making the VMGO an intrinsic part of campus life. Lin et al. (2017) found that frequent reinforcement of institutional principles improves students' alignment and acceptance of these goals.

5.Interactive and Engaging Communication

Another important topic in increasing VMGO acceptability was interactive and engaging communication strategies. Students preferred seminars, forums, and class discussions that allow them to participate more meaningfully with the VMGO. For example, one student stated, "Interactive activities like workshops could help students engage with the VMGO more meaningfully." This underscores the need for dynamic techniques that encourage active engagement and deeper comprehension rather than passive dissemination. Barkley et al. (2014) highlighted that interactive methods considerably boost student engagement and establish a closer link with institutional aims.

The perceived impact of the VMGO on students' motivation, academic engagement, and institutional pride

1. Inspiration for Academic Excellence and Professional Growth

The College of Computer Studies' Vision motivates students to strive for excellence in both their academic and professional interests. Many respondents stated that the Vision inspires them to set lofty goals, make positive contributions to society, and be a part of something bigger than themselves. As one student put it, the Vision gives students "a clear idea of what the college wants to achieve," encouraging them to "aim higher" and contribute to technological improvements. This sense of purpose not only drives academic performance but also inspires students to take on challenges and perform to their best abilities, as highlighted by one respondent who mentioned feeling motivated to work harder because "the college believes in my potential." Such sentiments align with studies that have shown how a clear institutional vision can promote a sense of belonging and purpose, leading to greater engagement and motivation (Lindh, 2016).

2. The Role of the Mission in Academic Engagement

The College of Computer Studies' Mission is viewed as a driving force in promoting academic engagement and molding students' learning experiences. Respondents repeatedly stated that the Mission inspires them to focus on values such as resilience, honesty, and social responsibility, which promote both academic and personal development. One student stated, "The Mission supports academic engagement by aligning the institution's values with students' learning experiences." The emphasis on practical skills, ethical values, and personal growth encourages students to see their learning as part of a larger context that goes beyond academic achievement. Recent research (Haskins & Eathorne, 2014) shows that incorporating institutional values into the academic experience promotes stronger involvement and commitment to the learning process.

3. Pride in the Institution through Goals and Objectives

Students regularly noted that the College of Computer Studies' Goals and Objectives inspired a strong sense of pride and belonging in them. Many students stated that knowing the college's commitment to promoting ethical behavior, global competitiveness, and academic success made them feel more connected to the institution's greater mission. According to one respondent, "The Goals and Objectives make me feel proud to be part of an institution that values not just academic success but also ethical conduct and global competitiveness." According to research by James et al. (2015), a well-communicated mission and set of goals can increase student pride and institutional loyalty, as students feel part of an institution that values their development.

4. Motivation through VMGO in Challenging Times

The College's VMGO (Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives) provides motivation amid difficult academic situations. Many responders recalled occasions in which they drew strength from the college's values, particularly resilience and commitment, to complete challenging projects or deadlines. One student stated, "The VMGO motivated me during a difficult project by reminding me of the importance of resilience and

commitment, which helped me stay focused and complete the task." Another student mentioned that reflecting on the college's emphasis on innovation and collaboration motivated them during a group project. This is consistent with research that shows how institutional values provide a psychological framework for overcoming obstacles and retaining motivation, particularly during stressful times (Fox & McDermott, 2015). The VMGO framework reminds students of the broader purpose behind their academic endeavors, helping them maintain focus and perseverance.

Conclusions

This study's findings emphasize the importance of the College of Computer Studies' Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) in molding students' academic experiences, career goals, and institutional pride. The VMGO's alignment with students' goals promotes motivation and engagement, assisting them in developing both technical and ethical abilities required for their professional development. Furthermore, the VMGO's emphasis on principles such as resilience, integrity, and global competitiveness enables students to overcome obstacles, perform to their full potential, and take pleasure in being a part of an institution dedicated to greatness. The VMGO's simple explanation and practical applicability increase its acceptance and relevance, ensuring that students not only understand but also embrace it as a guiding framework for their academic and professional journeys.

Recommendations

To increase the impact and acceptability of the VMGO, the College of Computer Studies should continue to maintain clarity and accessibility by reducing complicated words and making the VMGO available through a variety of communication channels. Furthermore, increasing student engagement through interactive and participatory activities like as workshops and forums may improve students' relationships to the VMGO. It is also critical to periodically emphasize the VMGO's relevance to students' academic and career objectives, ensuring that its values are consistent with their own aspirations and cultural views. These measurements would help to reinforce the VMGO as a motivator for student success, academic engagement, and institutional pride.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors hereby declare that this work was conducted in strict accordance with ethical research guidelines. All respondents were provided informed consent prior to participating, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's nature and objective. Respondents were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any moment, without consequence or detriment. The respondents' anonymity was protected throughout the research procedure, and all personal information was kept private. The respondents' well-being was prioritized, and all measures were taken to protect their rights and dignity. The author additionally confirm that no conflicts of interest arose during the course of the investigation. Every attempt was taken to avoid plagiarism, and all sources were appropriately mentioned. Additionally, the findings were interpreted

honestly and without bias. Finally, the findings of this study were used purely for research reasons, benefiting the academic and scientific communities.

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